

Arsenic chemistry in groundwater in the Bengal Delta Plain : Implications in agricultural system^ψ

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Arsenic (As) is of great environmental concern due to extensive contamination of groundwater in the Bengal delta basin with this toxin, thereby causing carcinogenic toxicity to millions of people. Soil contamination with arsenic input through the vehicle of contaminated groundwater, being used for irrigation, may prove detrimental to plant through its uptake to the toxic level. Indeed, the possibility of such toxin entering the human food web, along with biomagnification up in the food chain, through plant uptake of arsenic is of immediate concern. In this regard, chemistry of arsenic in groundwater-soil-plant system, its forms and distribution in soil, mobilization pattern and complexation behaviour, among others, are emerging areas requiring sustained research attention. The several remedial options to contain the toxic effect of arsenic in the soil-water-crop-human continuum also need to be evolved and tested. The present article gives an overview of these aspects while summarizing selected research findings of relevance of the present authors.

Arsenic (As), a toxic trace element, is of great environmental concern due to its presence in soil, water, plant, animal and human continuum^{1,2}. Its high toxicity and increased appearance in the biosphere has triggered public and political concern. Out of 20 countries in different parts of the world where groundwater arsenic contamination and human suffering therefrom have been reported so far, the magnitude is considered to be the highest in Bangladesh, followed by West Bengal, India^{3,4}. The scale of the problem is grave and unprecedented, covering a geographic area of 0.173 million square kilometer, while exposing 36 million people in the Bengal delta basin to risk^{5,6}. The widespread arsenic contamination in groundwater in different parts of West Bengal, distributed over 81 blocks, located primarily in five districts adjoining the river Bhagirathi, as well as the contiguous districts in Bangladesh, is of great concern².

The groundwater As concentration (50–1600 µg/L), reported from the affected areas of West Bengal, are several orders of magnitude higher than the stipulated Indian standard for the permissible limit in drinking water (50 µg/L, which is also the maximum acceptable concentration, MAC, for drinking water in Bangladesh, India and several other countries), as well as the WHO guideline value (10 µg/L)^{5,7–9}.

In West Bengal, the presence of As in groundwater in

concentrations exceeding maximum acceptable concentration was first detected in 1978, while the first case of As poisoning in humans was diagnosed at the School of Tropical Medicine in Calcutta in 1983¹⁰. The effect of ingestion of inorganic arsenic in drinking water and the health effects in adults has also been well established¹¹. The main focus of attention, until recently, has been exclusively on As contamination in groundwater-derived drinking water.

However, since groundwater is also used extensively for crop irrigation in the arsenic belt of West Bengal, the possibility of a build-up of arsenic concentration in agricultural soils and agronomic produce was anticipated. Actually more than 90% of the total groundwater used in the affected belt of West Bengal finds applications in the agricultural sector to meet the crop irrigational requirements^{2,10}. Indeed, As uptake by crop plants grown in soils contaminated with high concentration of arsenic, and irrigated with such arsenic contaminated groundwater has been reported by several workers^{12–17}. Such findings call for an immediate attention since what remains essentially a *point* and fixed source of arsenic contamination as for drinking water (e.g. a tubewell discharging contaminated water), may well become a *diffuse* and uncertain source of contamination when arsenic finds its way into the food web, accompanied with possible biomagnification up in the food chain². This as-

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

sumes added significance in view of the reported finding of higher (than permissible) level of arsenic in the urine samples of some people having no history of consuming arsenic contaminated drinking water (Dr. D. N. Guha Mazumdar, by private communication).

In this paper we propose to give a general description of occurrence and chemistry of arsenic in soil, interaction with ecosystem, entry of arsenic in the human food web, possibility of its biomagnification up in the food chain and potential remedial options to tackle the problem of arsenic contamination in groundwater.

Arsenic contamination in groundwater-soil system

Origin of arsenic in groundwater :

High arsenic concentration in groundwater is generally associated with the geothermal environments of volcanic deposits, geothermal systems and basin-fill deposits of alluvial lacustrine origin¹⁸. As regards the widespread arsenic contamination in groundwater in parts of West Bengal, India and Bangladesh, confined within the delta bound by the rivers Bhagirathi and Ganga-Padma, two major hypotheses, both of geogenic origin, have been proposed. According to the earlier one¹⁹, iron-containing minerals in the alluvial sediments, or formed *in situ*, combine with sulphur to form iron pyrites which have associated arsenic. The latter finds its way into groundwater through oxidation of arsenopyrite in aquifer sediments as atmospheric oxygen invades the aquifer in response to lowering of groundwater level by its large-scale abstraction for agricultural irrigation, especially for cultivation of summer (*boro*) paddy during the lean period of January to April when the groundwater recharge is at its minimum¹. This process would lead to the formation of iron sulphates and sulphuric acid.

This hypothesis is *not* consistent with the slightly alkaline status of groundwater in the affected delta, *nor* with its low (trace) concentration of sulphate, or high concentrations of bicarbonate, iron(II), arsenite, calcium and magnesium which tends to suggest an anoxic (reduced) aquifer conditions¹. Some workers²⁰⁻²² put forward the alternative hypothesis that the burial of the sediments, rich in organic matter, has led to strongly reducing conditions in groundwater aquifer, which is facilitated by high water table, fine-grained surface layers and widely practised wetland paddy cultivation, as well as microbial oxidation of sedimentary organic matter, depleting thereby the dissolved oxygen in groundwater. Arsenic is released when arsenic-rich iron oxyhydroxides, which are efficient arsenic-scavengers, are reduced in anoxic groundwater. Such reduction is driven by concentrations of sedimentary organic matter. Notwith-

standing these hypotheses, the exact sequence of geochemical reactions, leading to arsenic release in groundwater from the aquifer sediments, is still debated^{1,2}.

Arsenic concentration in groundwater of West Bengal :

The arsenic loading of the groundwater which is used as irrigation source varied from 0.06 to 0.53 mg/L in Nonaghata mouza of the Haringhata block of Nadia district in West Bengal¹³. A high degree of such contamination was also found in different parts of the affected-belt, to name a few, Gotera and Ghentugachi mouzas of Chakadaha block of Nadia district¹² (ranging from trace to 0.89 mg/L); Ambikanagar, Chakla, Iajpur and Chyangdana villages under Deganga block of North 24-Parganas district of West Bengal²³ (varying from 0.05 to 0.50 mg/L), etc. by a group of researchers at Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya^{12,13,23}.

Chemistry of arsenic in groundwater-soil environment :

Arsenic in groundwater is generally present as dissolved, deprotonated/protonated oxyanions, namely arsenites ($\text{As}^{\text{III}}\text{O}_3^{3-}$; $\text{H}_n\text{As}^{\text{III}}\text{O}_3^{(3-n)-}$, with $n = 1, 2$) or arsenate ($\text{As}^{\text{V}}\text{O}_4^{3-}$, $\text{H}_n\text{As}^{\text{V}}\text{O}_4^{(3-n)-}$, with $n = 1, 2$), or both, besides the organic forms. The toxicity of arsenic compounds in groundwater/soil environment depends largely on its oxidation state, and hence on redox status and pH, as well as whether arsenic is present in organic combinations. The toxicity follows the order : arsine [AsH_3 ; valence state of arsenic (As) : -3] > organo-arsine compounds > arsenites (As^{3+} form) and oxides (As^{3+} form) > arsenates (As^{5+} form) > arsonium metals (+1) > native arsenic metal (0). The arsenites are much more soluble, mobile, and toxic than arsenates in aquatic and soil environments. At pH 6–8, in most aquatic systems, both $\text{H}_2\text{As}^{\text{V}}\text{O}_4^-$ and $\text{HAs}^{\text{V}}\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ions (pentavalent arsenic forms) occur in considerable proportions in an oxidized environment (redox potential, $E_h = 0.2-0.5$ V), while the arsenous acid, $\text{H}_3\text{As}^{\text{III}}\text{O}_3$, is the predominant species (trivalent arsenic form) under reduced conditions ($E_h = 0-0.1$ V)^{2,24}.

The solubility, mobility, bioavailability and hence toxicity of arsenic in soil-crop system also depends on its chemical form, primarily the oxidation state^{25,26}. The inorganic forms of arsenic in soils and sediments include arsenites and arsenates. The organic forms, namely dimethylarsenic acid or cacodylic acid, which on reduction (e.g. in anoxic soil conditions) forms di- and trimethyl arsines, are also present²⁵. Under oxidizing aerobic conditions (characterized by high E_h), arsenic acid species and the arsenate oxyanions (H_3AsO_4^0 , H_2AsO_4^- , HAsO_4^{2-} , AsO_4^{3-}) (Fig. 1) are stable in soil environment¹⁸, whereas under mildly reducing conditions (such as one encounters in flooded paddy

soils with $E_h = 0-0.1$ V), and a pH range of 6 to 8, arsenous acid species and arsenite oxyanion species ($H_3AsO_3^0$, $H_2AsO_3^-$, $HAsO_3^{2-}$) are the stable forms (Fig. 1)¹. Furthermore, it has been recognized that As^{III} is more prevalent in soils of neutral pH range (and in most groundwater), as in the soils of the affected belt of West Bengal, India and Bangladesh, than otherwise thought, and hence is of concern. This is primarily because As^{III} exists as a neutral, uncharged molecule, namely arsenous acid, $H_3AsO_3^0$ ($pK_a = 9.2$), at the pH of neutral soils and most natural groundwater as one would expect based on the Henderson's equation¹.

Fig. 1. Fields of stability for dissolved forms of arsenic as a function of E_h and pH at 25°C¹⁸.

However, it ought to be emphasized that groundwater or soil solution, which is subject to affluxes and influxes, as well as circulation and also to man-made perturbations of groundwater due to its withdrawal, can not be expected to remain in thermodynamic equilibrium, it being very much of an open system (thermodynamically speaking), while Fig. 1 is based on the assumption of attainment of thermodynamic equilibrium among different As species in a closed system¹. Thus, more often than not, the ratio of concentrations of arsenic species, namely the ratio, $[As^{III}/As^V]$, in field soils does not quite agree with the ones computed from the observed redox potential (E_h) and the application of the Nernst's equation (at 25°C) to the redox reaction, namely

$$E_h \cong E_h^0 - 0.0295 \log \frac{[AsO_3^{3-}]}{[AsO_4^{3-}]} - 0.059 \text{ pH} \quad (1)$$

It is evident from eq. (1) that the proportion of As^{III} , and hence soluble arsenic level in soil, should increase substantially with diminishing E_h and increasing pH. Furthermore, at a high pH, the OH^- ion concentration would increase, causing displacement of As^{III} and As^V species from their binding sites through competitive ligand exchange reactions^{1,2}.

The dependence of arsenic sorption on pH of the sorption medium is governed largely by the nature of the soil colloidal fraction²⁷. A fall of arsenate adsorption was noted with increasing pH, but only at lower arsenate concentrations, which got reversed at a higher arsenate equilibrium concentrations²⁷. This trend was explained in terms of the varying electrostatic potential of the variable-charge soil colloidal surfaces with pH, solubility product principles, and buffering action of the arsenic salt used²⁷.

There have been both direct and indirect evidence to suggest that arsenic is held in soils and sediments by oxides (e.g. of Fe, Al, Mn) through the formation of inner-sphere complexes *via* ligand exchange mechanism^{25,27}. This is shown as follows^{28,29}.

or

However, the non-specific adsorption (through electrostatic mechanism) of arsenic also occurs at pH values below the point of zero charge (PZC) for a given adsorbent²⁸. As shown in the reaction scheme 2, the above stated ligand exchange tends to increase the negative charge of the soil colloidal fraction, for instance, of iron oxides, and thus push the PZC of the arsenic laden soil to lower pH. Indeed, this was shown by us¹⁴ to be the case in an incubation experiment wherein arsenic loading of soils from the affected site was found to shift the PZC to lower pH compared to the untreated soil, with concomitant increase in the negative magnitude of the variable-surface charge and the surface potential of the corresponding soil colloidal fraction (Table 1).

Soil acts as a major sink of As inflow to agroecosystems,

Table 1. Point of zero charge (PZC) and associated surface-charge characteristics of arsenic treated and untreated soils¹⁴

Parameter	Soils		
	Untreated soil	Treated with 800 mg As/kg	Treated with 1600 mg As/kg
pH (1 : 2.5) $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{H}_2\text{O} \\ 1 \text{ M KCl} \end{array} \right.$	6.33	7.86	7.88
	5.36	6.91	7.13
$\Delta\text{pH} = \text{pH}(\text{KCl}) - \text{pH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-0.97	-0.95	-0.75
PZC	6.00	5.85	5.50
$\text{pH}(\text{KCl}) - \text{PZC}$	-0.64	1.06	1.63
$\Psi_s \times 10^3$ in 1.0 M NaCl (V)	-8.05	-122	-143
$\Psi_p \times 10^4$ in 1.0 M NaCl (cm^{-2})	-1.87	-46.4	-54.9
$\Psi_v \times 10^4$ in 1.0 M NaCl (cm^{-2})	-0.43	-46.4	-63.2

thereby reducing the availability of the toxicant to the cropped species³⁰⁻³³. Thus, the capacity of soil to retain As gains substantial significance in relation to the passage of the toxicant in the groundwater-soil-plant/animal/human continuum. It is in this context that a thorough understanding of soil arsenic loading, different forms of arsenic pools present in the affected soils, along with their phytoextractability, soil-arsenic interactions, etc., is necessary to judge the capacity of soil for holding arsenic in its matrix, thereby reducing its accessibility to plant roots for uptake by crops.

Arsenic loading in soils of West Bengal :

Some of our research studies, conducted at the selected affected areas, revealed that the total and Olsen extractable (i.e. 0.5 M NaHCO₃, pH 8.5 – extractable As which constitutes the soil As pool amenable to plant uptake) arsenic (Table 2) varied from 8.40 mg/kg to 24.3 mg/kg and from 2.90 mg/kg to 15.8 mg/kg, respectively^{12,13,23}, in the given affected soils of West Bengal. The soil arsenic contents of these areas were generally higher than those reported for the soils of several other countries like Argentina, China, Italy, Mexico, France, Australia, etc².

Inorganic soil arsenic fractions from the affected soils were also fractionated into different soil arsenic pools, namely water soluble As (Ws-As), arsenic associated with Al compounds in soil, the so-called aluminium-bound As (Al-As), iron-bound As (Fe-As) and calcium-bound As (Ca-As), by following the sequential extraction methodology³⁴. The findings suggested that these inorganic soil As pools fell in the order : Ws-As < Al-As < Ca-As < Fe-As^{12,23}. In particular, the Fe-As fraction contributed 45 to 74.7% towards the total soil arsenic sequential sum^{12,23}.

Interaction of arsenic with organics in soil system :

The surface water bodies, located in the affected belt of the Bengal delta basin, have remained largely free of arsenic. This tends to suggest that the soil, which receives

Table 2. Total and Olsen extractable arsenic content (mg/kg) of selected arsenic affected soils of West Bengal, India^{12,13,23,33}

Location	Total arsenic (mg/kg)	Olsen (0.5 M NaHCO ₃ , pH 8.5) extractable arsenic ^a (mg/kg)
Gotera, Chakdaha block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India	20.1	9.80
Ghentugachi, Chakdaha block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India	23.0	15.8
Nonaghata Dakhinpara, Haringhata block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India	11.3	3.84
Nonaghata Uttarpara, Haringhata block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India	14.7	3.79
Iajpur, Deganga block, District-North 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India	16.5	6.40
Ambikanagar, Deganga block, District-North 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India	15.1	2.90
Chakla, Deganga block, District-North 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India	8.40	4.50
Baruipur, District-South 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India	24.3	4.20
Mullabelia, Haringhata block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India ^b	3.24	1.22

^aLabile form of soil arsenic pool which is amenable to crop uptake.
^bDeep tubewell command area.

As-contaminated water, acts as an effective sink to contain the toxin, thereby preventing the surface run-off to carry it to the adjoining water systems^{1,2}. The soil organic fractions including humic acid (HA) and fulvic acid (FA) behave as effective accumulators of toxic heavy metals, following the formation of metal-humate complexes (chelates) with different degrees of stability³⁵⁻³⁷. Besides, soil clays, aluminium oxides, iron oxides, especially the amorphous Fe and Al oxides in soil, also influence the arsenic retention by

soils, soil minerals and sediments^{1,38,39}. The stability constant (log *K*) of the complexes formed by the soil HA/FA with arsenic in the selected contaminated soils of West Bengal suggested that organo-arsenic complexes were quite stable, even in the presence of competing oxyanions such as phosphate and nitrate³⁷. Thus, improving the soil organic matter stock in the tropical soils of the arsenic-affected belt or West Bengal (which are relatively poor in native organic matter) by way of adopting the appropriate management practices (such as recycling of crop residues, incorporation of organic manure, etc.) is necessary for facilitating arsenic retention in the soils of arsenic-affected belt³⁷.

Retention of arsenic by soil minerals :

Several researchers investigated adsorption and stability of As³⁺ at the clay mineral-water interfaces and reported that alkaline solution (pH > 9.0), without clay mineral solids, caused homogenous oxidation of As³⁺ to As⁵⁺, whereas recovery of arsenic from As³⁺-treated clay mineral solids suggested enhanced oxidation of As³⁺ to As⁵⁺ by heterogeneous oxidation on kaolinite and illite surfaces, but not on montmorillonite surface^{38,39}.

The following reactions demonstrate the As³⁺ oxidation by oxygen at high pH, while that by Fe and Mn oxides in solution at lower pH values⁴⁰.

Retention of arsenic also depends on the concentration of phosphate in the soil in view of competitive phosphate-arsenate interactions for sorption *via* ligand exchange, at common sorption sites in soils and sediments^{1,32,36}. More of the latter will follow in the next section.

Interaction of arsenic with phosphorus :

Phosphorus (P) is one of the essential major plant nutrients for plant growth. Because As and P are both placed in group Vb, the interaction of As and P in soil-plant system is an important issue in respect of arsenic mobilization.

Indeed the indications are that these oxyanions would not be adsorbed independently in mixtures, but rather would tend to compete for some portion of the same type of adsorption sites²⁸.

Several workers showed that the presence of phosphate caused a reduction in arsenate adsorption, and that the re-

duction was much greater for the competitive effects of arsenate on phosphate adsorption by soil minerals, although a large variation in the degree of competition between these two oxyanions has also been reported^{24,32,39,41-43}. The relative affinity of As^V, P and Mo for the goethite and gibbsite surface was pH dependent and tended to be in the order, P ≈ As^V > Mo at neutral pH. Phosphate and As^V appeared to compete for a similar set of surface sites with phosphate depressing As^V sorption within the pH range of 2 to 11, though there was evidence that some sites were uniquely available for adsorption of either As^V or P³⁹.

The ligand exchange process may change the pH of the sorption system by raising the OH⁻ ion concentration (vide. Reaction scheme 2), which, in turn, may compete with phosphate or arsenic for surface complexation sites⁴³. This adds to the above stated fall of arsenate (and phosphate) adsorption by soils.

The findings from an incubation study tended to demonstrate the dependence of As release in soil solution of the As-contaminated soil samples (from the affected zone of West Bengal) on the applied phosphate and the organic manure, namely the farm yard manure (FYM), with FYM being able to bind As in soil matrix. This is illustrated by the step-wise multiple regression equations given in Table 3. This also reflects itself in the findings obtained from a supporting pot-culture experiment with rice crop, where application of FYM helped to moderate the arsenic accumulation in both the soil/plant. The latter tended to derive support from much higher yield of the crop observed in the arsenic-treated soils in presence of the said organic manure². Organo-arsenic complexation with humic/fulvic colloids of the native soil and the incorporated organic manures, which would be expected to moderate hazards of arsenic toxicity, was also demonstrated in the given study³⁷, thereby adding confidence to the trends of the above noted findings.

Arsenic in soil-plant system :

The input of arsenic to soil from various sources may prove detrimental to plant through its uptake to the toxic limit, thereby facilitating its entry into the food chain. There is also the possibility of biomagnification of the toxin as it travels up in the food web^{2,14}.

Several workers including the present authors have reported accumulation and transformation of As by a number of plant species grown in the arsenic affected areas. These crops (such as elephant-foot-yam, greengram, cowpea, sesame, groundnut, etc.) tended to show a build-up of arsenic (Table 4) in substantial quantities in different plant

Table 3. Stepwise multiple regression equations showing influence of different treatments on NaHCO₃ (pH 8.5) – extractable arsenic content (mg/kg) in selected soils of West Bengal, India³²

Soil	Regression equations	R ²
Gotera ^a	Y = 0.7951 + 0.4326 X ₁	0.618
	Y = 0.5665 + 0.4326 X ₁ + 0.0069 X ₂	0.757
	Y = 0.7713 + 0.4287 X ₁ + 0.0070 X ₂ - 0.4162 X ₃	0.899
	Y = 0.6087 + 0.4287 X ₁ + 0.0070 X ₂ - 0.4199 X ₃ + 0.0097 X ₄	0.943
Ghentugachhi ^a	Y = 0.7723 + 0.3848 X ₁	0.638
	Y = 0.965 + 0.3813 X ₁ - 0.3828 X ₃	0.788
	Y = 0.7717 + 0.3812 X ₁ + 0.0059 X ₂ - 0.3902 X ₃	0.931
	Y = 0.7007 + 0.3812 X ₁ + 0.0059 X ₂ - 0.3918 X ₃ + 0.0040 X ₄	0.940
Baruipur ^b	Y = 0.9837 + 0.0467 X ₄	0.530
	Y = 0.5476 + 0.4361 X ₁ + 0.0467 X ₄	0.872
	Y = 0.4195 + 0.4361 X ₁ + 0.0038 X ₂ + 0.0467 X ₄	0.895
	Y = 0.4861 + 0.4348 X ₁ + 0.0039 X ₂ - 0.1387 X ₃ + 0.0468 X ₄	0.901
Gayeshpur ^c	Y = 0.5077 + 0.3041 X ₁	0.384
	Y = 0.1738 + 0.3041 X ₁ + 0.0196 X ₄	0.596
	Y = 0.0541 + 0.3041 X ₁ + 0.0068 X ₂ + 0.0196 X ₄	0.779
	Y = 0.0851 + 0.3014 X ₁ + 0.0069 X ₂ - 0.2894 X ₃ + 0.1980 X ₄	0.866

^aMouza of Chakdaha Block, Nadia District; ^bBlock of South 24-Parganas District; ^cMouza of Haringhata Block, Nadia District.

Y = Extractable arsenic content in soil; X₁ = Arsenic addition; X₂ = Phosphorus addition; X₃ = FYM incorporation; X₄ = Incubation period.

Table 4. Arsenic content of different plant parts of the crops grown in the selected affected soils of West Bengal^{12,13,23}

Location of sites	Crops	Arsenic content (mg As/kg)			
		Root	Stem	Leaf	Economic produce ^e
Nonaghata, Haringhata block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India	Sesame	7.20	4.35	3.10	1.10
	Cauliflower	5.40	3.54	2.58	1.44
	Soybean	-	-	9.00	15.2
	Bitter gourd	-	11.6	12.2	12.5
	Tomato	-	8.50	6.70	5.00
	Rice (<i>boro</i>)	5.40	3.54	2.58	1.44
Gotera and Ghentugachi, Chakdaha block, District-Nadia, West Bengal, India	Elephant-foot-yam	-	8.30	4.60	4.23
	Green gram	6.00	5.70	5.28	4.10
	Cowpea	6.10	5.38	5.00	2.26
	Jute	11.0	9.30	3.69	4.20
	Groundnut	3.10	2.43	2.12	4.10
	Mustard	7.23	6.96	7.00	2.90
	Wheat	14.00	6.90	5.80	3.26
	Rice (<i>boro</i>)	8.30	7.32	8.42	10.0
Iajpur, Ambikanagar and Chakla, Deganga block, District-North 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India	Rice (<i>boro</i>)	61.4	48.3	35.3	11.6
	Pointed gourd	18.9	14.9	-	-
	Ridge gourd	-	-	-	31.4
	Okra	-	-	-	4.60
	Elephant-foot-yam	-	-	-	8.02
	Radish	-	-	-	13.4
	French bean	-	-	-	11.2
	Sugar beet	-	-	-	11.8
	Onion	-	-	-	25.2
	Mustard	13.0	3.51	4.58	10.3

parts^{12,13,23}. Indeed, pointed gourd, a vegetable creeper plant, has shown considerable arsenic loading when cultivated in the soils of West Bengal⁴⁴. A number of other vegetables, namely cauliflower, tomato, bitter gourd (Table 4) were also noted to accumulate arsenic in their economic produce^{12-14,23,33}. The arsenic content of the leaves, stem and potato tuber at harvest were 5.51, 9.34 and 10.2 mg/kg, respectively, when potato was grown with irrigation water with an arsenic loading of 0.22 mg As/L¹⁶. Thus, the distribution of arsenic content in plant parts generally followed the order (Table 4) : root > stem > leaf > economic produce.

Table 5. Critical arsenic contents in some soils of China leading to toxicity in rice plants⁴⁵

Soil	50 % growth reduction		No tillering		Death	
	As ^{III}	As ^V	As ^{III}	As ^V	As ^{III}	As ^V
	(mg/kg)	(mg/kg)	(mg/kg)	(mg/kg)	(mg/kg)	(mg/kg)
Paddy soil	130	160	170	210	210	310
Stagnogleyed paddy soil	75	85	110	115	169	269
Red sandy paddy soil	47	52	69	77	109	157

Reduction of arsenate to more toxic arsenite is facilitated by lowering of redox potential (E_h) which is encountered under anoxic soil conditions, with arsenite being more soluble and mobile than arsenate. Thus, rice plant is rather susceptible to arsenic toxicity since it is grown under submerged soil conditions (low E_h)^{1,2,36}. Thus, the total arsenic loading of rice crop was to the tune of 10 mg/kg and even more at 14% moisture level in the selected districts of Bangladesh¹⁷. In a pot-culture experiment, the critical arsenic contents in some paddy soils of China, leading to toxicity to rice plants, had also been worked out (Table 5)⁴⁵.

Fig. 2. Arsenic content in rice before and after parboiling (Source : Das, Ghosh, Saha and Sanyal (2003) (unpublished data)).

Further, the processing of rice (i.e. parboiling and milling, etc.) was found by the present authors to increase the arsenic loading (Fig. 2) in rice for both the traditional and the high yielding cultivars.

The concentrations of arsenic in flowering plants were found to be 0.114, 0.203, 0.214, 0.235 and 0.293 mg/kg when the levels of soil arsenic were 0, < 20, 20–30, 40–50 and >50 mg/kg, respectively⁴⁶. Tuberose and marigold, two important flowers of the country, were also reported to accumulate arsenic in their floral body with such arsenic content in the flower samples ranging from 1.8 to 3.6 mg/kg¹³. The toxicity of arsenic species in plant body is reported to follow the order : arsine (AsH₃) > As³⁺ > As⁵⁺ > MMA (monomethyl arsonic acid) > DMMA (dimethyl arsinic acid)⁴⁷.

Hyperaccumulation vis-à-vis detoxification of arsenic by plants/microbial species

Phytoremediation :

Phytoremediation is defined as the use of vegetation or other macro- and microscopic biota for *in situ* or *ex situ* treatment of contaminated soils, sediments and water where green plants degrade, assimilate, metabolise or detoxify inorganic and organic chemicals in soils to environmentally acceptable levels⁴⁸. In this context, phytoremediation may tend to offer a potentially useful avenue to address the problem of arsenic contamination of soil-crop system. Phytoremediation may also prove attractive due to its relative cost-effectiveness, coupled with its aesthetic nature, namely the use of plants for 'clean-up' activities. Indeed, a number of plant species, including the dominant wild species, growing in the arsenic-affected areas of West Bengal, have the capability to accumulate arsenic.

The reported hyperaccumulation of arsenic from the contaminated soils by the brake-fern, *Pteris vittata*, and its subsequent translocation into the above-ground biomass suggests that the plant-accumulated arsenic was present almost entirely in the toxic inorganic forms with the proportion of highly toxic As^{III} being in fact, much greater in the plant body than that of the less toxic As^V form, as compared to the distribution of these two forms in the contaminated soil in which the fern grows⁴⁹. Conversion of the plant-accumulated inorganic forms of the toxin to non (or less) – toxic organometallic forms by plant metabolism would certainly aid the detoxification process². Such detoxification within the plant body assumes importance particularly in view of the report that arsenic in plant residues may be mobilized by a unicellular algae, namely *Polyphusa peniculus* resident in normal (moist) agricultural soils⁵⁰.

A scan of literature reveals a number of plant/microbial species, known for arsenic accumulation/or as bioindicator, which can effectively remove arsenic (and other heavy metals) from the aquatic system, for instance, to the tune of 170 and 340 mg As/g dry weight of water hyacinth in its stem and leaves respectively⁵¹, when grown in a pond containing 10 mg As/dm³. However, such accumulated arsenic in water hyacinth (*Eichornia crassipes*) is also liable to leaching out in the water body, particularly so on decomposition of such aquatic weed. Consequently, appropriate precaution has to be exercised while interpreting the arsenic status of aquatic environment by water hyacinth accumulation⁵².

A number of microbial species (e.g. the bacterial species, namely *Proteus* sp., *Escherichia coli*, *Flavobacterium* sp.; *Corynebacterium* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp., the fungus, namely *Candida humicola*; the freshwater algae, namely *Chlorella ovalis*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Oscillatoria rubescens*) have been reported to possess varying degrees of arsenic accumulating abilities².

Several weed species, identified by the present authors, normally found along with crops like rice, potato, jute, mustard, etc. growing on arsenic contaminated soils (2–14 mg As/kg soil) and subjected to irrigation (given to the desired crops) with arsenic contaminated groundwater, were noted to accumulate considerable amounts of arsenic in their biomass. Table 6 demonstrates the extent of such arsenic accumulation by these weed species⁵³.

Table 6. Arsenic content of different weed flora in the existing crop fields of selected arsenic contaminated area of West Bengal⁵³

Weeds	Arsenic content (mg As/kg)	
	Stem	Leaf
<i>Ludwigia parviflora</i>	3.12	–
<i>Enhydra</i> sp.	12.3	–
<i>Filmbristylis</i> sp.	14.1	28.1
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	2.40	–
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	4.50	14.1
<i>Croton sparsiflora</i>	12.2	10.4
<i>Lantana camara</i>	8.40	10.2
<i>Vitis trifolia</i>	4.30	7.91

However, it is worth noting in this context that such accumulation of arsenic does not necessarily lead to its detoxification *per se*^{1,2} unless the plant-accumulated toxin is effectively detoxified within the plant body by its metabolic processes. Hence, the success of such phytoremediation technique would depend on establishing a desirable plant community. For this, a systematic search for phyto-

accumulating or phytoexcluding plant species is necessary. Some of the techniques in this field, that may prove useful, include phytodegradation (the process in which the given plant species are capable of metabolizing and destroying the contaminant within the plant tissues), phytovolatilization or biotransformation (the process employing microorganisms and plants to transform the toxicants into the volatile forms to escape to the atmosphere), rhizofiltration (the process in which plants, used for clean-up, accumulate the toxicants), etc.⁵³. This would certainly be a useful tool for remediating arsenic contamination in an effective manner.

Epilogue :

Arsenic toxicity of contaminated drinking water in humans in many parts of the world, including West Bengal, India, has deservedly received increasing concern. Arsenic toxicity in livestock and other animal species like poultry, fish and sea food has been given comparatively much less attention². On the other hand, arsenic contamination in agroecosystem, that acts as a conduit for the passage of the toxicant to human population *via* food web, came under serious consideration only recently².

The present write-up has demonstrated that, equal if not greater, attention is necessary for understanding the complex aspects of accumulation of arsenic in the food web *vis-à-vis* that in drinking water alone, and its ultimate passage to the human populations. For this, a comprehensive approach is necessary to combat the present arsenic crisis. Some of the potential remedial options aimed at reducing the toxic effect of arsenic in agricultural systems include optimum conjunctive use of ground and surface water (e.g. use of harvested rainwater) irrigation with pond-stored excess rainwater and groundwater, recharge of the groundwater resource with rainwater, and enhancing water use efficiency for the agricultural crops by way of adopting appropriate soil and irrigation water management strategies. The cultivation of low water-requiring, farmer-attractive cropping sequences, especially during the lean period, is also another important option to arrest or minimize the entry of the toxin in the food chain. Establishment of cost-effective rhizosphere biodegradation, phyto-stabilization, phyto-accumulation, etc., may also provide for useful means to combat the situation. Hence, the implementation of long-term technical alternatives to reduce dependence on arsenic contaminated resources, awareness and involvement of the affected population for the confinement through mass movements, gradually leading to the zeroing of arsenic related problem, and promotion of international networking in support of arsenic mitigation are necessary².

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